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Research Article

Crafting and Advancements of Pippali and Cissus Quadrangularis Anti-Inflammatory & Anti-Rheumatic Herbal Ointment

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ABSTRACT

Crafting and Advancements of Pippali and Cissus Quadrangularis Anti-Inflammatory & Anti-Rheumatic Herbal Ointment” Are Viscous semi-solid formulations called ointments are applied externally to the skin or mucous membranes. Using two traditional medicinal herbs, Cissus quadrangularis and pippali (long pepper), the study's objective was to create and assess an herbal ointment having anti-inflammatory and anti-rheumatic qualities. A fusion technique and trituration were used for the preparation. Throughout the development phase, three distinct formulations were used: Placebo: This formulation was made as a control and contained no active component, Pippali was incorporated into the formulation for F-1 (Pippali-based formulation). This resulted in a black-looking ointment. F-2 (formulation based on Cissus quadrangularis): Pippali was swapped out for Cissus quadrangularis in this formulation. When the dark green ointment was applied to the skin, it caused a slight easing of pain. F-3 & F-4 (Combined formulation): By combining Pippali and Cissus quadrangularis, this formulation improved absorption and bioavailability while also enhancing anti-inflammatory and anti-rheumatic properties. With a pH of 5.9, this ointment was determined to be well-balanced and skin-friendly. The prepared ointments exhibited good appearance, spread ability, and stability under typical storage conditions. Importantly, the combined formulation (F- 4) displayed major anti-inflammatory effects and effectively reduced inflammation, while the reference drug alleviated pain. No skin irritation or phase separation occurred during storage, indicating that the ointment is safe for topical use. Pippali, recognized for its pain-relieving and anti-inflammatory effects, was incorporated into the formulation for its ability to diminish swelling and inflammation and alleviate pain. The developed herbal ointment, containing Pippali and Cissus quadrangularis, proved to be a stable, effective, and safe product for topical use, exhibiting promising anti-inflammatory and anti-rheumatic properties. The formulation was well-tolerated on the skin, showing no signs of irritation or phase separation, and demonstrated beneficial effects in reducing inflammation and pain.

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INTRODUCTION

Aim:

The aim of this project is to develop an ointment using Pippali (Long Pepper) and Cissus quadrangularis (Veldt Grape) Fine Powder, which have Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Rheumatic properties. “Crafting and Advancements of Pippali and Cissus Quadrangularis Anti-Inflammatory & Anti-Rheumatic Herbal Ointment”

Objective:

To standardize Pippali and Cissus quadrangularis for their active Anti- Inflammatory and Anti-Rheumatic compounds. To formulate a stable and

effective ointment using these plant Fine Powders. To evaluate the Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Rheumatic activity of the developed ointment through in vitro and in vivo testing. To assess the physical properties of the ointment, such as texture, spread ability, and skin compatibility. To conduct stability studies to ensure the ointment’s shelf-life and efficacy. To determine the safety and tolerability of the ointment through skin irritation and irritation tests.

Description Of Materials and Equipment’s:

Materials Used:

Table. No :01

Sl. No	Material Names	Suppliers Details	Uses
1.	White petroleum	Lodha petrol	Base for Ointment & Soothing Effect
2.	White beeswax	Shree Giri corporation	Emulsification and Moisture Retention
3.	Wool fat	Goldlan cosmetic	Improves Spread ability
4.	Hard paraffin	Delhi wax refinery	Stability and Shelf-Life Enhancement
5.	Dried powder of Pippali longum	Chender kala trading co.	Pain Relief (Analgesic Effect) & Anti-Inflammatory Properties
6.	Dried Fine powder of Cissus quadrangularis	A M Nutratch PVT LTD Prakash chemical international Pvt	Anti-Inflammatory Properties

Equipment’s Used:

Table No :02

Sl. No	Equipments	Source
1)	Weighing balance	RP-E001
2)	Sieves	RP-E002
3)	Water bath	RP-E008
4)	Ointment slab	RP-E021
5)	Ointment spatula	RP-E014
6)	Thermometer	RP-E006

7)	Ph meter	RP-E017
8)	Incubator	RP-E008
9)	Brookfield viscometer	RP-E100

Uses Of the Materials Used in The Formulation:

Description Of Materials: -

Pippali: -

Fig No :01

Synonym: - long pepper, Piper Longum

Biological source: -it consists of dried flowering vine of piper longum linn.

Family: - Piperaceae

Uses:

The fruit of long pepper are claimed to be efficacious in cold, cough, asthma, hiccough, splenic disorders and also as liver tonic. It is used in digestive issues, respiratory problems and infections

Cissus Quadrangularis: -

Fig No:02

Synonym: - Veldt grape, Adamant creeper

Biological source: -Cissus Quadrangularis is obtained from the stems of the Perennial plant of the Grape family.

Family: - Vitaceae

Uses: -

Cissus plays role in improving bone health, heal fractures, sprains. Cissus is rich in vitamin C and vitamin E.

Wool Fat: -

Fig no: 03

Synonym: - lanolin, hydrous wool fat, adeps lane, anhydrous lanolin.

Biological source:- it is obtained from the wool of the sheep *Ovis aries* linn., belonging to the family bovidae .it is the secretion of sebaceous gland of sheep deposited on to the wool fibres. The chief constituents of wool fat are cholesterol and oxocholesterol , unsaturated monohydric alcohols of the formula $C_{27}H_{45}OH$. Wool fats also contain aliphatic alcohols such as cetyl ceryl and

carnaubyl alcohol. Wool alcohols BP/EP are prepared by the saponification of crude lanolin and the separation of the alcohol fraction. Wool fat is used as an emollient base for cream and ointment.

Uses: -

It is used as water absorbable ointment base. Used as common ingredient and base for water soluble creams and cosmetics.

Hard Paraffin:

Fig no :04

Synonym: - Paraffin wax

It is purified mixture of solid hydrocarbons and obtained from petroleum.

it is colorless or white translucent, odorless, tasteless waxlike substance.

it is used to harden or soften the ointment base.

Uses: -

it is used to stiffen ointments and creams and to coat capsules and tablets.

it can also open pores and remove dead skin cells.

Paraffin wax may be used to help relieve pain in people with osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, fibromyalgia, and other joint mobility issues.

White Bees Wax:

Fig no :05

Synonym:- cera alba , cire blancha , weisses wachs

Biological source :-beeswax is obtained from the honey comb of the bees apis mellifera .

Family: - apidae

Uses: -

Beeswax helps in water incorporation to form an emulsion.

it is used in preparation of ointments, plasters, and polishes.

it used in the manufacturing of candle, molds in dental and electronic industries, cosmetic for lipstick, face cream.

Cetosteryl Alcohol: -

Fig No :06

Synonym: - Cetearyl alcohol, Cetyl alcohol
Cetearyl alcohol is a chemical found in cosmetic products. it is a white, waxy mixture of cetyl alcohol and stearyl alcohol, both are fatty alcohols. they are found in animals and plants like coconut and palm oil.

Uses:-

It is used in the cosmetic industry as an opacifier in shampoos, or as an emollient, emulsifier or thickening agent in the manufacture of skin creams and lotions. it imparts an emollient feel to the skin and can be used in w/o emulsion and o/w emulsion, anhydrous formulations.

Preliminary Test for Pippali:

Table No :03

Test	Observation	Inference
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A. Test For Flavanoids-		
1.Shinoda test- To extract, add 5ml 95% ethanol /t-butyl alcohol, few drops of conc .HCL and 0.5g magnesium turnings.	Orange ,pink, red to purple colour appras	Present
2.Sulphuric acid On addition of sulphuric acid (66%-80%) flavones and flavnol dissolve into it .	Gives red to bluish solutions Flavones gives orange	Present
B.Test For Saponin -		
1.FOAM TEST- Shake the drug extract or dry powder vigorously with water.	Persistent stable foam observed.	Absent
C. Test For Carbohydrates-		
1.BENEDICT 's test mix equal volume of of benidict's reagent and test solution in the test tube . heat in boiling water bath for 5min .	Orange colours observed	Present
2.Fehling's test- Mix 1ml Fehling 's reagent and test solution ,boil for 1min water bath for 5min to 10 min .	Brick colour precipitate is observed.	Present
E. Test For Protiens-		
1.BURET TEST- To 3ml of test solution. add 4%of NaOH and few drops of 1% CuSo4.	Violet pink colour appears	Present
2.PRECIPITATION TEST- Add absolute alchohol 5%, lead acetate,copper sulphate	Test solution give colloidal precipitate	present
G. Test for Alkaloids-		
1.Dragendroff 's test - To 2-3 ml filtrate, add few drops Dragendroff's reagent	Orange brown precipitate is formed.	Present

Preliminary Test for Cissus Quadrangularis: -

Table No:04

Test	Observation	Inference
A. Test For Protiens-		
1.BIURET TEST: Test solution was treated with equal volume of 10% sodium hydroxide solution and two drops of 1% copper sulphate solution.	Formulation of violet or pink colour.	Present
2.Xanthoproteic Test: Few drops of conc.nitric acid add two ml of extract and mixed well.	Formulation of light to dark yellow colour.	
B.Test For Saponins :		

1.Foam Test : In this test 0.5g of extract was added in 10-20 ml of water .	Formation of frothing which persisted for 60-120sec .	Absent
C. Test for carbohydrates		
1.Benedict's test: Test solution was mixed with 1-2 drops of Benedict's reagent and it is boiled in water bath,wait for few minutes.	Formation of reddish-brown ppt.	Present
2.Molish's test: Filtrate was treated with 1-2 drops of alcoholic α - naphthol solution in a test tube.	Formation of the violet ring.	Present
D.Test for Alkaloids-		
1.Wagner's test: A fraction of extract was treated with 3-5 drops of Wanger's reagent.	Formation of reddish brown ppt .	Present
2.Mayer's test- Filterates were treated with Mayer's reagent .	Formation of yellow colour ppt.	Present
E. Test for Phenonls:		
1.Ferric chloride test : Extracts was treated with 3-4 drops of ferric chloride solution	Formation of bluish black colour.	Present
F. Test for Tannis:		
1. Gelatin test: To the extract add 1% gelatin solution which containing sodium chloride .	Formation of white ppt.	Present
G.Test for Flavonoids:		
1.Shinoda test: Crude extract was mixed with few fragments of magnesium ribbon and add drop wise conc.HCL in that mixture .	Formation of pink scarlet colour.	Present
I.Test for Glycosides:		
1.Killer Killani test: Test solution was treated with 1-2 drops of glacial acetic acid and ferric chloride solution mixed well .than add few conc. Sulphuric acid.	Formation of two layers,lower layer is reddish brown and upper layer is acetic acid layer which turn in bluish green.	Present

Formulation And Development

Formulation of ointment using pippali and cissus quadrangularis: -

Ointments are homogeneous translucent semi-solid preparation, most commonly a greasy, thick oil (oil 80 % - water 20%) intended for external application to three skin or mucous membrane.

Drug ingredients can be dissolved, emulsified, or suspended in the ointment base. Ointment is mainly used as a emollient or protective for skin. Comparative formulation and development of piper longum and cissus quadrangularis ointment Ingredients

Table No:05

Sno	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4 Optimized Formula	Placebo Ointment
1.	White petrolatum	0.5mg	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm
2.	White beeswax	0.5mg	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm
3.	Wool fat	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm
4.	Hard paraffin	7.0mg	7.5gm	6.5gm	8.5gm	8.0gm
5.	Dried powder of Pippali longum	1.0gm	0gm	1.0gm	1.0gm	0gm
6.	Dried powder of Cissus quadrangularis	0gm	1.0gm	1.0gm	1.0gm	0gm
7.	Cetostearyl alcohol	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm
	Total weight of ointment	10gm	10gm	10gm	10gm	10gm

F-1	F-2	F-3& F-4	Placebo

Crafting and Advancements of Pippali and Cissus Quadrangularis Anti-Inflammatory & Anti-Rheumatic Herbal Ointment” prepared by using fusion followed by Trituration method.

Methodology:

Preparation Method:

The ointments were prepared by following these steps:

1. In a water bath at 70°C, the measured quantities of hard paraffin and Ceto stearyl alcohol were melted.
2. In a separate beaker, the mixture of wool fat and white soft paraffin was melted in a water bath at 70°C.
3. The contents of both containers were blended and swirled until they cooled.
4. The contents were checked for any foreign particles and decanted if needed.
5. The preparation was packed, labeled, and dispensed.

6. The ointment was formulated using Pippali and Cissus quadrangularis by the fusion method, followed by trituration.

Fusion Followed by Trituration Method: -

1. When ointments contain a number of solid ingredients with different melting points, it is necessary to melt them using hot water bath in decreasing order to their melting point. all the components are melted accordingly. the medicaments are slowly added to the melted mass stirred thoroughly until mass cools down and gives a homogenous product. In this method all the ingredients are fused together
2. In this method all the solid medicaments are finely powdered. accurately weigh the required quantity of ointment base. then triturate them properly. add the remaining amount of base until the medicament is uniformly mixed.

Evolution Of Herbal Ointment:

Morphological Evaluation:

Physical Attributes: The color, smell, and appearance of the ointment is observed.

Herbal ointment was evaluated for morphological parameters showed in table. The colour of prepared formulation was blackish green. The odor of prepared formulation was aromatic, spicy, earthy. Texture and smoothness were acceptable as per requirement of cosmetic formulation

Physicochemical Evaluation

Explantation to be included

Test for Non – Irritancy:

The bases used for ointments, may cause allergic reaction. Patch test is used for evaluation Of Non irritancy. 5 human volunteers are selected for this test. Observation of type of pharmacological action is observed. No visible reaction or erythema with edema and vesicular erosion should occur. A good ointment base shows no allergic reaction.

Test For Rheological Properties:

Viscosity is the one of the important parameters of semisolid preparation. It should be easily removed from the container and easily applied to the skin cone and plate viscometer or Brookfield viscometer is used to determine the viscosity of the preparation.

Test for Microbial Growth:

After preparing the agar medium the designed ointment was infected using the steak – plate method on the agar medium , and a controlled was created by leaving out the ointment . the plates were put in a incubator where they will spend the next 24 hours at 37 °c . the plates were removed from the incubator after the incubation period and the microbial growth was examined and contrasted.

3.Physico-Chemical Evalutation

Table No 06.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation				
		Blank	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Colour	Off white	Blackish	Dark green	Greenish black	Greenish black
2	Odour	No odour	Aromatic	Spicy and earthy	Spicy and earthy	Spicy and earthy
3	Texture	Smooth and greasy				

pH

The Ph of herbal ointment was found to be in range of 5.4 to 6.2 which is good for skin pH . The formulation was shown pH near to skin required.

pH - Table

Table No 07

Sr. No	Formulation	pH
1	Blank	5.4
2	F1	5.8
3	F2	6.0
4	F3	6.2
5	F4	6.2

Washability:

Table No :08

Sr. No	Formulation	Wahability
1	Blank	Easily washable
2	F1	Easily washable
3	F2	Easily washable
4	F3	Easily washable

Irritancy Test:

The table below shows the result of irritancy test. During irritancy trials, the formulation displayed absence of irritation, redness, and edema. The formulation is safe for skin.

Table No :09

SR. No	Irritancy test	Result				
		Blank	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Irritation	no	no	no	no	no
2	Redness	no	no	no	no	no
3	Edema	no	no	no	no	no
4	Swelling	no	no	no	no	No

Test Of Microbial Growth -

There was no sign of microbial growth after 24 hrs of incubation at 37degree celcius and it was comparable with the control.

Evaluation Of Herbal Ointment

Table No :10

Sr. No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Colour	Blackish	Dark green	Blackish green	Blackish green
2	Odour	Aromatic	Spicy & Earthly	Spicy & Earthly	Spicy & Earthly
3	Irritancy	no	no	no	no
4	pH	5.8	6	6.2	6.2
5	Washability	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable
6	Test for microbial growth	no	no	no	no

7	Texture	Smooth and greasy	Smooth and greasy	Smooth and greasy	Smooth and greasy
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Stability Test

A stability study was conducted over a period of 3 months to evaluate the degradation and overall stability of the herbal ointment when stored at room temperature (approximately 25°C). During this period, the ointments were regularly monitored for any changes in appearance, consistency, color, odor, pH, and the presence of any physical degradation or phase separation.

Results:

Appearance: The ointments maintained their original appearance throughout the study, with no discoloration, separation, or visible changes observed in any of the formulations.

Consistency: The texture and spread ability of the ointments remained consistent, showing no signs of hardening or thinning over time.

Color: The color of the ointments (black for F-1, dark green for F-2, and a combination of both for F-4) remained stable and did not change during the 3- month period.

Odor: No off-odors or rancid smells were detected, indicating that no chemical degradation occurred.

pH: The pH of the ointments remained within the expected range (around pH 5.9), suggesting that the formulation remained stable and skin-friendly.

Phase Separation: No phase separation occurred, and the formulations remained homogeneous throughout the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An Anti-Rheumatic and Anti-Inflammatory herbal ointment were formulated using Pippali (Piper longum) and Cissus quadrangularis. The formulation process involved several trials (Placebo, F1, F2, F3, and F4) to optimize the product. After thorough evaluation of its physical, chemical, and Microbiological properties, the final ointment formulation was prepared and labeled as F4. The formulations F1 and F2 initially included

active components, but after further evaluation, F3 and F4 were found to have better non-Irritancy, Stability, Balanced PH properties. Based on the evaluation criteria, F3 was optimized as the best formulation. As a result, the F3 formulation was finalized as the Most effective option. The final 10g batch of the optimized ointment demonstrated strong anti- rheumatic, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic (pain-relieving) properties, making it a promising choice for Topical use.

CONCLUSION:

“Crafting and Advancements of Pippali and Cissus Quadrangularis Anti-Inflammatory & Anti-Rheumatic Herbal Ointment” The combination of Cissus quadrangularis (Veldt Grape) and Pippali (Piper longum) in herbal ointments exhibits encouraging potential in both conventional and contemporary therapeutic uses, per the aforementioned result. While Pippali is well-known for its anti-inflammatory and digestive qualities as well as its capacity to increase the bioavailability of other herbal compounds, Cissus quadrangularis is highly respected for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory qualities. These ointments offer calming and therapeutic advantages by harnessing the healing qualities of plant-based substances, frequently with fewer adverse effects than synthetic substitutes. Herbal ointments are a common option for people looking for kinder, natural treatments, whether they are used for small burns, skin irritations, or pain relief. These ointments offer calming and therapeutic advantages by harnessing the healing qualities of plant-based substances, frequently with fewer adverse effects than synthetic substitutes. Herbal ointments are a common option for people looking for kinder, natural treatments, whether they are used for small burns, skin irritations, or pain relief. Herbal ointments containing Cissus

quadrangularis (Veldt Grape) and Pippali (Piper longum) exhibit encouraging promise for both conventional and contemporary therapeutic uses. The anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and bone-healing qualities of *Cissus quadrangularis* are highly valued, whereas pippali is well-known for both its anti-inflammatory and its capacity to increase the bioavailability of other herbal compounds

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